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ConcePTION

WP2, Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.10: Best practice guidance for evaluation of case reports on pregnancy and signal detection

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Abstract

Medication use in pregnancy is common, yet for many medicines, adequate evidence on fetal safety is slow to accumulate meaning that safety data are often lacking. It is also common for safety data to be conflicting, which may result from variation in the observational research methods which are used to generate them. Evidence for the safety of medication use in pregnancy is mostly provided by post-marketing observational studies which use a variety of data sources and methodological techniques. Emerging safety data are therefore often highly heterogenous, which impedes the ability to assimilate data from different studies. Improving the speed at which medicines with teratogenic effects are identified is key to avoiding wide-scale use in pregnancy, thereby preventing harm, which may be life-limiting or lifelong. Equally, improving the speed at which high-quality evidence indicating safety can be generated would increase the confidence of both healthcare professionals and their patients regarding gestational medication use, thereby optimising effective treatment of maternal medical conditions during pregnancy.

Work Package 2 (WP2) of the ConcePTION project focussed on sources of primary data collection, where information about medication exposure and pregnancy outcome is collected directly from pregnant women and/or their healthcare providers (HCPs). A primary objective within WP2 was to develop a series of operational recommendations and guidelines for primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance datasets to optimise and standardise data collection techniques, analysis, and reporting. The aim with providing these guidelines was to attempt to improve the standardisation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data to increase data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities.

This report provides an overview of the data evaluation and guideline outputs from WP2, and explores their future application in pregnancy pharmacovigilance research. Outputs include: (i) a novel tool to assess the clinical quality of information in real-world pregnancy pharmacovigilance case reports; (ii) a novel reference framework of the core data elements which should be included in primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data collection systems; (iii) statistical analysis and reporting recommendation guidelines for single arm pregnancy medication safety studies investigating pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes.

Widespread adoption of these expert consensus recommendations for data collection, case report evaluation, statistical analysis and reporting of PregPV data, is fundamental to achieving the aim of faster generation of high-quality evidence on medication safety in pregnancy to inform clinical care.

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List of abbreviations

Table 1: List of abbreviations in the report

Abbreviation	Explanation
PregPV	Pregnancy pharmacovigilance
WP	Work Package
TIS	Teratology Information Services
HCP	Healthcare providers
CDM	Common Data Model
DAP	Data Access Provider
SRS	Spontaneous Reporting System
MAH	Marketing Authorization Holder
EMA	European Medicines Agency
WHO	World Health Organization
CDE	Core Data Element

Introduction

Maternal medication use is common during pregnancy [1], and it is estimated that more than 80% of women use at least one prescribed medicine whilst pregnant [2, 3]. When including over-the-counter medicines, it is estimated that nearly all pregnant women will use at least one medicine [4, 5]. Due to a combination of ethical restrictions and practical complexities, safety data are usually established through observational/non-interventional studies in the post-marketing setting. Unfortunately, there is currently no standardised or systematic approach to post-marketing pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PregPV) data collection. As such, evidence on the safety of a particular medication is typically slow to accumulate [6], leaving pregnant women and their healthcare providers with insufficient [7, 8] or conflicting [9] information when making clinical decisions about medication use.

In 2019, the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) launched the ConcePTION project in acknowledgement of the societal obligation to rapidly reduce the uncertainties around the safety of medication use in pregnancy and breastfeeding [10]. Work Package 2 (WP2) of the project focussed on sources of primary data collection, where information about medication exposure and pregnancy outcome is collected directly from pregnant women and/or their healthcare providers (HCPs). Broadly the systems which utilise primary source data collection techniques include spontaneous reports, data collected by Teratology Information Services (TIS), pregnancy registries (disease and medication specific), clinical cohorts, and enhanced pharmaceutical industry pharmacovigilance studies. These approaches have been utilised for decades to provide data for observational PregPV research. Whilst numerous longstanding national and international primary source PregPV datasets exist, these worldwide data are geographically fragmented and exist in various non-standardised formats, in some cases, sub-optimally designed for this bespoke purpose. This results in variable data quality and impedes the ability to rapidly combine raw data and/or to assimilate the evidence generated from different studies to decrease the time taken to provide reliable conclusions about the safety of medicinal products.

A primary objective within WP2 was to develop a series of operational recommendations and guidelines for primary source PregPV datasets to optimise and standardise data collection techniques, analysis, and reporting. The aim of the approach to improve standardisation was to increase data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities, thereby improving the ability to provide high-quality evidence-based statements about the risks and benefits of medication use in pregnancy in a shorter timeframe.

Two tasks within the WP were devoted to achieving this key objective:

- **Task 2.6: Proposing a secure and trusted environment for reporting medication exposed pregnancy cases.** Based on the characteristics of a trusted and effective system defined during a stakeholder workshop undertaken in the early stages of the project and findings from demonstration study 1 (Analysis and signal detection of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature), recommendations on how to instil and operate an environment where HCPs and women can report pregnancies will be described. The process for reporting pregnancy exposures by HCPs to the system will be developed and formalised. The system may then be used to collect, share and analyse (using automated data mining algorithms, database flagging / counting) enhanced PregPV data.

- **Task 2.7: Guidelines, recommendations and training materials.** Guidelines for the generation of evidence on drug safety assessment in pregnancy based on spontaneously reported pregnancies will be drafted using expertise with existing methods and experience of the demonstration projects. These will include guidance on the standards for the reporting and assessment of PregPV case reports in peer review journals.

This report provides an overview of the outputs and publications on the various studies conducted in WP2 which have contributed to learning within these tasks.

Proposing a secure and trusted environment for reporting medication exposed pregnancy cases

To aid the combination of distinct datasets, WP2 explored the feasibility of developing a common data model (CDM) which would allow data to be combined from numerous Data Access Providers (DAPs). Theoretically, this approach would allow similar datasets to be interrogated from one centrally defined data analysis location, while the data access providers maintain control of their data without involving the transfer of sensitive data. Although a robust system allowing for an automated information exchange of data from spontaneous reports and literature-based case reports already exists (using the ICH-E2B(R3) standard [11]), this is not optimised for PregPV research purposes. In addition, such an exchange for other primary data collections for PregPV purposes (e.g. TIS, registries and enhanced PV programmes) do not exist.

Early feasibility work established the complexity of attempting to develop a pregnancy optimised CDM which would allow data to be combined from such a variety of heterogeneous data sources. It was therefore decided to focus this part of the project on spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) and literature-based data only.

Singular cases of adverse events observed from daily clinical practice are either published in the literature in the form of case reports or submitted as (spontaneous) reports to Marketing Authorization Holders (MAHs; pharmaceutical companies), national pharmacovigilance centres or international regulatory agencies like the European Medicines Agency (EMA), or other bodies involved in drug safety monitoring such as the World Health Organization (WHO). These observations have been proven to be a useful tool in the detection of safety information in respect to the safety of registered medicinal products used during pregnancy, but they all have their shortcomings and are not optimized for PregPV data capture [12-16], which may have an impact on the quality of information and the way these data are analysed. As a first step in defining a CDM for data combination, the nature and content of SRS data were described, whilst assessing the capture of data that are relevant for the analysis of medication exposure safety during pregnancy. Existing methods to assess the quality of the data contained within SRS were not designed to specifically assess the quality of pregnancy data [17-18]. Methods were therefore developed to assess the clinical quality of information in real-world PregPV case reports, and subsequently validated.

Summary of key outputs and findings: Important elements needed to assess the clinical quality of information for a risk assessment of medicinal products used during pregnancy, by means of two surveys and two focus group discussions amongst PregPV experts [19]. A novel method for the assessment and evaluation of the quality of PregPV data was developed and validated. The validation found that the tool provided a method with less inter-rater variability compared with a quality assessment by experts of pregnancy-related PregPV data [20].

Publications supporting these findings:

- 1) Yrea R J Van Rijt-Weetink, Khoezik Chamani, Toine C.G. Egberts, Florence P.A.M. Van Hunsel, David J Lewis, Laura M Yates, Ursula Winterfeld and Eugene P. Van Puijenbroek. Elements to Assess the Quality of Information of Case Reports in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data - a ConcePTION project. *Front. Drug Saf. Regul.*, 29 June 2023 *Sec. Maternal-Fetal Medicine Volume 3 - 2023* | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdsfr.2023.1187888>

Background: To assess the risk of exposure to a medicinal product during pregnancy in an individual case report, the necessary information should be present, complete and clearly described. Previously designed grading tools were not developed for pregnancy pharmacovigilance data.

Objective: This study aims to identify the elements that are necessary to assess of the quality of information for risk assessment of medicinal products used during pregnancy. This is a first step in the development of a validated method to assess the clinical quality of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data.

Methods: Potential information elements were determined by means of an expert focus group discussion and a survey based on its outcome. This provided an overview of possible information elements to be selected. For the final selection of the elements, a second survey and subsequent focus group discussion was used.

Results: Twenty-one information elements within seven categories were identified: information related to the association itself, the event, exposure to the medicinal product, maternal factors, pregnancy, labour, and the child.

Conclusions: This study identified elements considered necessary in the assessment of quality of information of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data, via an extensive four-step process.

- 2) YRJ van Rijt-Weetink, ACG Egberts, FPAM van Hunsel, DJ Lewis, LM Yates, U Winterfeld, EP van Puijenbroek. Validation of a Novel Method to Assess the Clinical Quality of Information in Pregnancy-Related Pharmacovigilance Case Reports: A ConcePTION Project. *Drug Saf.* 2024 Mar;47(3):261-270. doi: 10.1007/s40264-023-01389-y. Epub 2024 Jan 6.

Background: To assess the causal relationship between a medicinal product and a reported event, relevant information needs to be present. Information elements for assessing cases of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy were predefined and used in a new tool to assess the quality of information. However, the extent in which the presence or absence of these predefined information elements is associated with the overall clinical quality of these cases, as evaluated by pharmacovigilance experts, remains uncertain.

Objective: We aimed to validate a novel method to assess the clinical quality of information in real-world pregnancy pharmacovigilance case reports.

Methods: The clinical quality of case reports regarding medicinal product exposure and pregnancy-related outcomes was appraised from spontaneous reports, literature, Teratology Information Services (UK and Switzerland), The Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, the Gilenya pregnancy registry and the Enhanced PV programme of Novartis. Assessment was done by means of the novel standardised tool based on the presence and relevance of information, and by expert judgement. The novel tool was compared to the expert assessment as the gold standard expressed as the area under the receiver operating characteristic curves, after which the sensitivity and specificity were calculated. Inter-rater variability was determined by means of weighted Cohen's kappa.

Results: One hundred and eighty-six case reports were included. The clinical quality score as assessed by the novel method was divided into three categories with cut-off values of 45% (poor to intermediate) and 65% (intermediate to excellent). Sensitivity was 0.93 and 0.96 for poor to intermediate and intermediate to excellent, respectively. Specificity was respectively 0.52 and 0.73. Inter-rater variability was 0.65 (95% confidence interval 0.53–0.78) for the newly developed approach, and 0.40 (95% confidence interval 0.28–0.52) for the gold standard assessment.

Conclusions: The tool described in this study using the presence and relevance of elements of information is the first designed, validated and standardised method for the assessment of the quality of information of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data. This method confers less inter-rater variability compared with a quality assessment by experts of pregnancy-related pharmacovigilance data.

- 3) YRJ van Rijt-Weetink, J van Gendt, ACG Egberts, FPAM van Hunsel, DJ Lewis, LM Yates, U Winterfeld, EP van Puijenbroek. Quality of Clinical Information in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data Sources – a contribution of the ConcePTION project. Submitted for publication (Jul-24).

Background: Good documentation of adverse events related to medicines is essential for assessment of safety signals. Information on the clinical quality of primary pregnancy safety data sources is lacking.

Objective: to assess the differences in clinical quality of various sources of primary pregnancy PV data.

Methods: Fifty reports of exposures to medicines during pregnancy were collected from: spontaneous and literature reports from EudraVigilance, European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS), the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, enhanced PV programmes (EPV), and patient support

programmes (PSP). Reports were standardized and anonymized, after which their clinical quality was assessed. Mean scores per source were compared using ANOVA (analysis of variance test). Results: Mean clinical quality scores were 89.0% (SD 10.1%) for the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, 77.1% (SD 13.3%) for TIS, 64.7% (SD 20.5%) for EPVs, 49.5% (SD 16.2%) for PSPs, 40.9% (SD 21.6%) for spontaneous reports, and 38.6% (SD 18.0%) for literature reports. All were statistically significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) except for spontaneous versus literature reports (mean difference 2.2%, $p = 0.99$) and spontaneous reports versus reports from PSPs (-8.6%, $p = 0.14$).

Conclusions: For data sources specifically designed for pregnancy data collection, the clinical quality of information generally outweighed sources designed to capture general safety information. EPV methods showed better scores for clinical quality compared to spontaneous reporting data for pregnancy PV.

Guidelines, recommendations and training materials

Core data elements for PregPV Studies

As there is currently no standardised or systematic approach to the post-marketing assessment of medication safety in pregnancy, data generated through pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PregPV) research can be heterogenous and difficult to interpret. With the aim of improving the standardisation of data collection procedures and, thereby, improve data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities, a reference framework of core data elements (CDEs) for collection in primary source PregPV studies was developed. The development of these recommendations involved a robust scoping review of published guidelines and data dictionaries of established PregPV data collection systems. Experts in PregPV undertook extensive discussions and consideration of the validity and necessity of each data element identified. It is hypothesised that an optimised and standardised approach to data collection could be an important component in decreasing heterogeneity of outcome reporting, thereby improving the confidence in the synthesis of results from different studies in systematic literature reviews and meta-analysis studies. Furthermore, a standardised approach will facilitate the combination of high-quality and detailed data from multiple sources using a common data model approach, which in turn would facilitate faster generation of evidence. This framework serves as both guidance for researchers developing new data collection systems, and also provides a standard data format which existing data can be transformed into in.

Summary of key outputs and findings: The finalised listing of CDEs comprises 98 individual data elements, arranged into 14 tables of related fields. These data elements are openly available on the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) website (<http://www.entis-org.eu/cde>) [21]. A demonstration project was undertaken to assess the ability of several public and private DAPs using different primary data sources focusing on multiple sclerosis, to map their respective data variables and definitions with the CDE recommendations framework. Data access providers participating in this study presented a very high proportion of variables matching the CDE items, indicating the feasibility with the alignment of CDE definitions and harmonisation of data by different stakeholders [22].

Publications supporting these findings:

- 4) Richardson JL, Moore A, Bromley RL, Stellfeld M, Geissbühler Y, Bluett-Duncan M, Winterfeld U, Favre G, Alexe A, Oliver AM, van Rijt-Weetink YRJ, Hodson KK, Rezaallah B, van Puijenbroek EP, Lewis DJ, Yates LM. Core Data Elements for Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Studies Using Primary Source Data Collection Methods: Recommendations from the IMI ConcePTION Project. *Drug Saf.* 2023 May;46(5):479-491. doi: 10.1007/s40264-023-01291-7. Epub 2023 Mar 28. PMID: 36976447

Introduction and objective: The risks and benefits of medication use in pregnancy are typically established through post-marketing observational studies. As there is currently no standardised or systematic approach to the post-marketing assessment of medication safety in pregnancy, data generated through pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PregPV) research can be heterogenous and difficult to interpret. The aim of this article is to describe the development of a reference framework of core data

elements (CDEs) for collection in primary source PregPV studies that can be used to standardise data collection procedures and, thereby, improve data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities. **Methods:** This CDE reference framework was developed within the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) ConcePTION project by experts in pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiology, medical statistics, risk-benefit communication, clinical teratology, reproductive toxicology, genetics, obstetrics, paediatrics, and child psychology. The framework was produced through a scoping review of data collection systems used by established PregPV datasets, followed by extensive discussion and debate around the value, definition, and derivation of each data item identified from these systems. **Results:** The finalised listing of CDEs comprises 98 individual data elements, arranged into 14 tables of related fields. These data elements are openly available on the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) website (<https://www.ents-org.eu/cde>). **Discussion:** With this set of recommendations, we aim to standardise PregPV primary source data collection processes to improve the speed at which high-quality evidence-based statements can be provided about the safety of medication use in pregnancy

- 5) Guillaume Favre, Jonathan L. Richardson, Alan Moore, Yvonne Geissbühler, Valentine Jehl, Alison Oliver, Svetlana Shechtman, Orna Diav-Citrin, Maya Berlin, Tal De Haan, David Baud, Alice Panchaud, Anil Mor, Meritxell Sabidó, Sabrina de Souza, Christina Chambers, Yrea R. J. van Rijt-Weetink, Eugène P. van Puijenbroek, Laura M. Yates, François Girardin, Michael Stellfeld*, Ursula Winterfeld*. * The authors contributed equally. Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project. *Drug Safety* (2024) 47:227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40264-023-01384-3>

Introduction and Objective: The ConcePTION project aims to improve the way medication use during pregnancy is studied. This includes exploring the possibility of developing a distributed data processing and analysis infrastructure using a common data model that could form a foundational platform for future surveillance and research. A prerequisite would be that data from various data access providers (DAPs) can be harmonised according to an agreed set of standard rules concerning the structure and content of the data. To do so, a reference framework of core data elements (CDEs) recommended for primary data studies on drug safety during pregnancy was previously developed. The aim of this study was to assess the ability of several public and private DAPs using different primary data sources focusing on multiple sclerosis, as a pilot, to map their respective data variables and definitions with the CDE recommendations framework.

Methods: Four pregnancy registries (Gilenya, Novartis; Aubagio, Sanofi; the Organization of Teratology Information Specialists [OTIS]; Aubagio, Sanofi; the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, Lareb), two enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes (Gilenya PRIM, Novartis; MAPLE-MS, Merck Healthcare KGaA) and four Teratology Information Services (UK TIS, Jerusalem TIS, Zerifin TIS, Swiss TIS) participated in the study. The ConcePTION primary data source CDE includes 51 items covering administrative functions, the description of pregnancy, maternal medical history, maternal illnesses arising in pregnancy, delivery details, and pregnancy and infant outcomes. For each variable in the CDE, the DAPs identified whether their variables were: identical to the one mentioned in the CDE; derived; similar but with a divergent definition; or not available.

Results: The majority of the DAP data variables were either directly taken (85%, n = 305/357, range 73–94% between DAPs) or derived by combining different variables (12%, n = 42/357, range 0–24% between DAPs) to conform to the CDE variables and definitions. For very few of the DAP variables, alignment with the CDE items was not possible, either because of divergent definitions (1%, n = 3/357, range 0–2% between DAPs) or because the variables were not available (2%, n = 7/357, range 0–4% between DAPs).

Conclusions: Data access providers participating in this study presented a very high proportion of variables matching the CDE items, indicating that alignment of definitions and harmonisation of data analysis by different stakeholders to accelerate and strengthen pregnancy pharmacovigilance safety data analyses could be feasible.

Statistical analysis and reporting recommendations

Single arm pregnancy medication safety studies are typically among the first datasets to emerge during post-marketing safety monitoring of medication safety in pregnancy. The standardisation of these datasets is therefore expected to improve the rate and quality of evidence to inform risk benefit recommendations. Building on previous standardisation work from the ConcePTION project [21-23], a series of recommendations on the statistical analysis and reporting of this design of safety studies was developed, focussing on pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes. The guidelines were developed via a web-based Delphi review method. Preliminary recommendations were adapted from a statistical analysis plan developed within ConcePTION to standardise and optimise the analysis of data from various medication in pregnancy safety sources. These recommendations, along with their scientific justification and examples of how to calculate and describe exposure and outcome incidences, were subsequently critiqued and improved through a series of Delphi review rounds which allowed the expert panel to provide open but anonymised feedback.

Summary of key outputs and findings: A set of 30 recommendations were developed, 19 strongly advised while 11 were included for consideration (where their implementation may be beneficial for supplementing data communication). These recommendations included descriptions of how to analyse and/or report: (i) the study sample, (ii) medication exposure; (iii) maternal outcomes; (iv) pregnancy and birth outcomes; and (v) fetal and neonatal outcomes.

Publications supporting these findings:

- 6) Jonathan L. Richardson, Alan Moore, Michael Stellfeld, Yvonne Geissbühler, Ursula Winterfeld, Guillaume Favre, Christina Chambers, Evelin Beck, Marlies Onken, Katarina Dathe, Michael Ceulemans, Orna Diav-Citrin, Svetlana Shechtman, Alison M. Oliver, Kenneth K. Hodson, Dee-Dee Schiller, Amalia Alexe, Eugène P. van Puijenbroek, David J. Lewis, and Laura M. Yates. Delphi method consensus on statistical analysis and reporting recommendations for single arm pregnancy medication safety studies investigating pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes; a contribution from IMI-ConcePTION. Under peer review. A manuscript of this work was submitted for publication in late October 2024 (currently under peer review with Drug Safety).

Background and Objective: Standardisation of current approaches to safety monitoring of medications used in pregnancy is lacking. As a result, it often takes years or decades to provide the quality and quantity of data which are needed to reliably inform on the risks and benefits of gestational medication use. Introducing standardised procedures for data collection, analysis and reporting may help improve data quality and the speed of data generation. The objective of this study is to provide a series of recommendations on the statistical analysis and reporting of single arm pregnancy medication safety studies.

Methods: A Delphi study was undertaken to acquire consensus agreement on recommendations from experts with extensive knowledge and experience in conducting pregnancy drug safety studies. Preliminary recommendations were adapted from a statistical analysis plan developed within ConcePTION to standardise and optimise the analysis of data from various medication in pregnancy safety sources. These recommendations, along with their scientific justification and examples of how to calculate and describe exposure and outcome incidences, were subsequently critiqued and improved through a series of Delphi review rounds which allowed the expert panel to provide open but anonymised feedback. As a final step, agreement to inclusion scoring was assessed using a five-point Likert scale.

Results: The recommendations were produced with the input of 20 experts from nine countries. The methodology applied in this study produced a set of 30 recommendations spread over five themes. These included descriptions of: (i) the study sample, (ii) medication exposure; (iii) maternal outcomes; (iv) pregnancy and birth outcomes; and (v) fetal and neonatal outcomes. Of the 30 recommendations, 19 were strongly advised while 11 were included for consideration where implementation may be beneficial for supplementing data communication. The final set of recommendations all scored highly on the Likert scale (median score 5, IQR 4 to 5), with a high proportion of the expert review panel scoring the recommendations ≥ 4 ($n=420/448$, 93.8%, 95% CI; 90.9 to 95.7%).

Conclusion: Use of the finalised set of recommendations as a framework for designing statistical analysis and data reporting plans should be encouraged to help standardise published evidence around

medication use in pregnancy.

Discussion

Medication use in pregnancy is common, yet for many medicines, adequate evidence on fetal safety is slow to accumulate meaning that safety data are often lacking. It is also common for safety data to be conflicting, which may result from variation in the observational research methods which are used to generate them. Evidence for the safety of medication use in pregnancy is mostly provided by post-marketing observational studies which use a variety of data sources and methodological techniques. Emerging safety data are therefore often highly heterogenous, which impedes the ability to assimilate data from different studies. Improving the speed at which medicines with teratogenic effects are identified is key to avoiding wide-scale use in pregnancy, thereby preventing harm, which may be life-limiting or lifelong. Equally, improving the speed at which high-quality evidence indicating safety can be generated would increase the confidence of both healthcare professionals and their patients regarding gestational medication use, thereby optimising effective treatment of maternal medical conditions during pregnancy.

Work Package 2 (WP2) of the ConcePTION project focussed on sources of primary data collection, where information about medication exposure and pregnancy outcome is collected directly from pregnant women and/or their healthcare providers (HCPs). Broadly the systems which utilise primary source data collection techniques include spontaneous reports, data collected by Teratology Information Services (TIS), pregnancy registries (disease and medication specific), clinical cohorts, and enhanced pharmaceutical industry pharmacovigilance studies.

A primary objective within WP2 was to develop a series of operational recommendations and guidelines for primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance datasets to optimise and standardise data collection techniques, analysis, and reporting. The aim with providing these guidelines was to attempt to improve the standardisation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data to increase data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities, to decrease the time taken to provide high-quality evidence-based statements about the risks and benefits of medication use in pregnancy.

This report provides an overview of the data evaluation and guideline outputs from WP2, and explores their future application in pregnancy pharmacovigilance research. Outputs include: (i) a novel tool to assess the clinical quality of information in real-world pregnancy pharmacovigilance case reports; (ii) a novel reference framework of the core data elements which should be included in primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data collection systems; (iii) statistical analysis and reporting recommendation guidelines for single arm pregnancy medication safety studies investigating pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes.

Conclusion

Widespread adoption of these expert consensus recommendations for data collection, case report evaluation, statistical analysis and reporting of PregPV data, is fundamental to achieving the aim of faster generation of high-quality evidence on medication safety in pregnancy to inform clinical care.

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